

THE IMPACT OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND EMOTIONAL STABILITY ON COGNITIVE PERFORMANCE: MEDIATING ROLE OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND EMOTIONAL BALANCE

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DOI:

Keywords:

The Physical Education, Emotional Stability, Cognitive Performance, Emotional Intelligence, Emotional Balance & Mediation

Article History

Received on 19 Feb, 2026

Accepted on 12 March, 2026

Published on 16 March, 2026

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Abstract

This cross-sectional study examines that how interaction of influence of physical education, emotional stability, and emotional intelligence, emotion balance as the mediating variables to determine that physical education and emotional stability have on the academic performance of university students. According to the theoretical background, the study hypothesized some potential relationships among research variables in particular context. The students completed the questionnaire, and researchers gathered secondary data regarding academic and cognitive performance used on the basis of formal simple sampling method. The physical education data were gathered through self-reporting throughout term and degree of perceived effort engaged, emotional state stability was assessed using the validated measures of emotional stability and mental health, emotional self-control was assessed using validated methods, and performance assessed using standardized tasks in the form of the cognitive performance to test hypothesized relationships among variables in order to extract new information and produce the desired and leading outcomes. These findings indicate that in spite of the covariates, both higher emotional stability and active involvement in physical education are positively, statistically significant predictors of cognitive functioning. These relationships were partially mediated by variables, emotional intelligence, and emotional balance, which are two elements of emotional functioning. Physical education and emotional stability were combined and anticipated emotional intelligence and emotional balance were in turn connected to cognitive functioning. The mediation paths were found to be statistically significant after the covariates were adjusted. The information described in this report implies that improvement of emotional functioning led to higher levels of the cognitive functioning, as well as higher amounts of organized physical education. An example of how this data can be used is in curriculum design, campus wellness program, and incorporation of possible mechanisms that can allow tracking of cause-and-effect relationships into the future into the long study.

INTRODUCTION

The correlation between work out and academic achievement is an issue which is researched by numerous researchers and many of them confirm that exercise enhances attention and focusing on activities [1]. The emotional intelligence is cognitive function with balance in the emotional stability, emotional balance and physical education, the interaction of emotions and physical exercise with the various cognitive results [22]. The emotional stability is another factor, which influences cognitive functioning and can influence people in terms of concentration, information processing and problem solving. Consequently, there are studies that indicate that the cognitive performance of students is positively influenced by exercise performed in physical education from different perspectives [3]. It is not merely the subject to be taken but the pillar of whole upbringing and contributes to the physical and emotional development of the brain of student in different circumstances.

The physical exercise enhances the circulation of blood and oxygen to the brain that also assists in information processing, attention and concentration. This enhances the concentration of the mind to acquire knowledge [4]. The emotional stability has the positive relationship with the ability of individual to possess and cope with stress and to possess balanced emotional control. The exercise also motivates the development of the brain cells and enhances the connection within the brain, particularly the hippocampus [4]. The exercise is also beneficial in alleviating stress, and reducing fatigue, and anxiety of students in different situations. All these contribute to the mental clearness and school performance. All this aid in maintaining focus on issues [6]. Individuals who possess stable personalities in relation to emotions are in a better position to cope with stress and anxiety and forget other aspects like decision making and focus less easily towards the outcomes.

The emotional stability and emotional balance are also interrelated and are the most significant ones that relate physical education and cognitive performance to emotional stability. Emotional balance assists in recovering resilience, setback, maintaining motivation and positive attitude that assist in cognitive processes [7]. Emotional intelligence refers to capability to control and perceive emotions to an astounding close that can be used to enhance social competence and interactions. Problems that are intricate and emotionally demanding are also resolved through the help of emotional stability and intelligence [9]. All these are useful with social environment and positive learning. The students who have higher levels of emotional

intelligence are able to concentrate and control emotions being more helpful in activities that require more effort [10]. The more is balanced the less emotional overload the students and assists in working memory and cognitive control.

The emotional stability is contained within calmness in face of trouble everywhere. Ambivalent emotions are favorable in dropping negative emotions that can interfere in the mental functions such as thinking and listening. The learning and remembering things involve mental processes in cases where there is balance in students' feelings [11]. The correlation amid physical education, emotional stability, emotional intelligence, and emotional balance proves the existence of the comprehensive system of comprehending the role of physical activity and emotional control in the processes of the mind [12]. Emotions are stable to keep a good degree of arousal required in cognition towards the desired determinations. According to system, it is necessary to consider the significance of the comprehensive educational programs that not only cover the mental and physical context but also the emotional and mental health to enable students to attain improved mental results in learning.

The phenomenon can enhance, cover and equate learning prospects better over interdisciplinary focused assistance to optimize encouraged personal and academic growth. The relations amid the educational interventions, physical activity, emotional balance, and emotional intelligence should be valued since it executes educational interventions [12]. The emotional stability is the primary wellbeing and it is boosted as a result of physical education. It is a myth that the field of physical education is about fitness. The fact that emotional balance and emotional intelligence have to mediate possesses in terms of education and the emotional wellbeing and the cognitive performance one accomplishes [14]. One of the most important qualities one needs is emotional stability which is an outcome of the biochemical reaction on the physical activity that soothes person emotionally their emotions with help of competitive sports and movement activities that are aimed at teamwork.

Through these interactions, it can be known that physical activities make students interested and release their endorphins, which can contribute to achieving the required emotional stability among the students [15]. The endorphins have beneficial effect on mood and can be used to deal with stress by lowering adrenaline and cortisol statements as positive emotions/ stability and cognitive performance are axiomatic [16]. The self-confidence and self-esteem, are closely related to emotional stability and positive emotions, respectively, affect the

cognitive performance and movement activities can significantly improve the emotional stability. This skill of coping with disappointment becomes better with practice [17]. The ability to achieve personally significant goals within exercise activities will probably increase self-worth and emotional strength and is positive feedback. In this regard, cognitive overload results in emotional instability and reduced capacity to concentration.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The existing literature provide sufficient clues to address complex nexus of physical education, emotional stability, and cognition, literature provided emphasized the nature and applicability of such issues to the stakeholders, which include educators, psychologists, policy makers, and learners [10]. The literature provided opined that physical education can be used to promote the emotional stability by means of teaching students' various strategies that can be used to relieve anxiety, stress, as well as negative feelings [14]. It is the inter-relationships of variables that are important to the overall development of the students in manner that increases their academic performance and their emotional and psychological health by the secretion of endorphins and other neurochemicals that increase well-being [18]. and calmness and is directly linked to the cognitive performance of the students in the institutions to realize the diverse leading outcomes for anticipated developments.

Their engagement in the sports and other physical activities also help the learners to improve their emotional stability and their resilience and coping strategies, which are also significant in achieving emotional stability [22]. The students who can do nothing but work on development of their emotions study profoundly and perceive more information better, and they also burnout less because they can get the cognitive overload [27]. The emotionally stable students cope with academic stress more easily that leads to better cognitive abilities and increased attention, the increased memory and better problem-solving skills. The emotional intelligence involves ability to handle and handle emotions [31]. Emotional stability refers to the capacity to avoid emotional outbursts, manage emotions, and be emotionally stable and this is what emotional intelligence entails relationships among stability, performance, intelligence, balance is complete picture to the approach the students.

It is influence of psychosocial stressors and the difficulties of life transition that have impacted the emotional, psychosocial and cognitive aspects of the performances of the students that has promoted the crucial nature of role of physical and emotional functions under analysis,

and of emotional intelligence specifically, in context of the psychosocial framework of higher education [2]. In context of psychosocial context of higher education, psychosocial mechanism, emotional intelligence, emotional balance, defines presence of positive emotional resources, and successful involvement of resources in the processes of cognition [5]. Stability of emotions as the capacity to achieve consistent emotional condition and to recuperate swiftly to stressors in environment also, to a degree, of the execution of the functions of emotions [7]. The functions of the elements of cognition, that is, attention, memory, emotional, but functioning thereof, and level of physical activities for outcomes.

A student who is emotionally stable is less affected by anxiety, extent of emotional exhaustion and mood swings that interrupts the process of attention, cognitive load and how the executive operates in decision making [10]. The inter-disciplinary and multi-dimensional role of physical education as a psychologically stable student on healthy psychosocial and cognitive perspectives of the performance is a physiological and psychological complex [13]. The moderating effects of emotional intelligence and emotional balance, integration with physical and academic training [16]. The physical activities in the education offers students regular and balanced involvement to long lasting physical activities which promotion of blood flow in brain, positively influencing the neural pathways and the functions of neurotrophic factors, the brain derived neurotrophic factors which enhances storage and retrieval of the information and the controlled functions of the executive activities.

Emotional stability enables to allocate the cognitive resources to resolve problems in academic manner as opposed to emotional way that heightens capacity of cognitive functions that forms the foundation of the effort channeled to the emotions to enhance effectiveness of the cognitive functions [18]. Even supposing higher education students are under stress due to their academic studies, social problems, and not knowing what career they want to pursue, emotional stability is a psychological protective element enables cognitive functioning [20]. Besides physiological effect to body, physical education develops required characteristics to discipline, goal-setting, self-regulation, and stress management, which are in demand of a long-term commitment to a cognitive activity [21]. The emotional stability and emotional related and different in meaning whereby balance are capability of individual to manipulate his/her positive and negative feelings in the medium term.

The physical education lessens stress, anxiety, and depression symptoms and elevates positive emotions and psychological well-being and, therefore, leads to emotional balance. Learners that attend physical education classes are more alert and better at concentrating, as well as more cognitively flexible [24]. This results in enhanced information processing and performance on the higher-order thinking tasks. The emotional stability builds on this balance by decreasing emotional instability and building emotional stability [27]. This emotional balance enables the capability of having attention and it integrate many elements of information. The role of physical education on emotional stability and cognitive functioning is also great, yet tangible through intelligence and emotional balance presence [30]. Emotional balance is best combination of emotions as it boosts cognitive functioning due to less worry and over thinking which interferes with thinking process.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is quantitative in nature that aims to examine relationship in chasing the hypotheses and reaching conclusion. The positivism approach was used to chasing relationships among research variables (physical activity, life satisfaction, and motivation) of study. The research approach specifies the way through which data is collected from the respondents by retrieving them to reach their answers about variables of research in order to reach required conclusion through justification towards desired outcomes. The population of interest in this research is students hailing from colleges in Punjab, Pakistan wherein 2890 students from colleges wherein a sample is drawn from population (351), has been extracted by using the sampling formula widely used in the social research studies. Thus, 351 questionnaires were distributed among which 334 were recollected and used for analysis. Similarly, the random simple technique was used to access the population of study which comes under the non-probability technique to ensure required data from diverse dimensions. Also, both secondary and primary data were used to collect data from respondents and from existing knowledge databased to analyze data to reach conclusion. The questionnaires were adopted from previous studies. Similarly, 5-point Likert scale was used to record responses of respondents about research issues in particular context to access respondents and achieving desired outcomes.

RESULTS OF STUDY

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
Physical Education	340	1.30	4.80	3.1306	.78607
Emotional Stability	340	1.33	4.67	3.0158	.81436
Emotional Intelligence	340	1.70	4.70	3.3491	.67446
Emotional Balance	340	1.60	4.60	3.4092	.66657
Cognitive Performance	340	1.63	4.70	3.3331	.61411

The descriptive statistics is important tool in research analysis that provides significant leading information about the research variables of different nature concerning the mean of responses about the variables and minimum and maximum response rates regarding variables through the different statements along with the standard deviation in responses towards the variables of the current study. The results of present study provide significant information concerning research variables that are within the acceptable range and thus significantly described the description of the research variables.

Reliability Analysis

Variables	Items	Excluded	Cronbach Alpha
Physical Education	10	02	0.87
Emotional Stability	10	03	0.82
Emotional Intelligence	10	01	0.88
Emotional Balance	10	02	0.79
Cognitive Performance	10	03	0.92

The reliability is important and significant tool that is used for ensuring the internal consistency among the research variables for measuring the accuracy and sequence in alignment towards the research issues. The results of current study provide significant information concerning these variables that are within the acceptable range (.6), likewise the physical education (CA = 0.87), emotional stability (CA = 0.82), emotional intelligence (CA = 0.88), emotional balance (CA = 0.79) and cognitive performance (CA = 0.92), which thus significantly describe the internal as well as required consistency among research variables of different nature under considerations in present research study.

Correlation Analysis

		Correlations				
		[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]
Physical Education [1]	Pearson Correlation	1	.368**	.448**	.426**	.602**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	340	340	340	340	340
Emotional Stability [2]	Pearson Correlation	.368**	1	.260**	.282	.314**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.131	.000
	N	340	340	340	340	340
Emotional Intelligence [3]	Pearson Correlation	.448**	.260**	1	.453**	.540**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	340	340	340	340	340
Emotional Balance [4]	Pearson Correlation	.426**	.282	.453**	1	.554**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.131	.000		.000
	N	340	340	340	340	340
Cognitive Performance [5]	Pearson Correlation	.602**	.314**	.540**	.554**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	340	340	340	340	340

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation procedure was used to examine the association with regard to the direction and strength on relationship concerning the association among the research variables like physical education, emotional stability, emotional intelligence, emotional balance as well as the cognitive performance. The outcomes of correlation procedure provide significant information concerning the association which are positive and significant in current study like physical education and cognitive performance ($R = .602$ & $P = .000$), emotional stability and cognitive performance ($R = .314$ & $P = .000$), emotional intelligence and cognitive performance ($R = .540$ & $P = .000$), and emotional balance and cognitive performance ($R = .554$ & $P = .000$), and therefore hypothesis was accepted from results that provides significant clues towards the determination of cause-&-effect analysis in study.

Regression Analysis

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	SEE
1	.725a	.526	.520	.42526

Regression Analysis

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	67.263	4	16.816	92.984	.000b
	Residual	60.584	335	.181		
	Total	127.847	339			

Regression Analysis

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
		Coefficients		Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.636	.151		4.197	.000
	Physical Education	.264	.036	.338	7.323	.000
	Emotional Stability	.080	.031	.107	2.594	.010
	Emotional Intelligence	.205	.041	.225	5.009	.000
	Emotional Balance	.276	.041	.299	6.753	.000

a. Predictors: Physical Education, Emotional Balance, Stability & Emotional Intelligence

b. Dependent Variable: Cognitive Performance

The regression procedure was used to examine the hypothesized relationships concerning the hypothesis about the cause-&-effect relationship among the research variables likewise physical education, emotional stability, emotional intelligence, emotional balance as well as the cognitive performance to confirm prediction of cognitive performance over physical education, emotional stability, emotional intelligence, emotional balance. The results of regression provide significant information about the prediction which significantly examine the cognitive performance through the predicting variables like 52.6% change and individual influence like physical education ($\beta = .264$ & P-value = .000), emotional stability ($\beta = .080$ & P-value = .010), emotional intelligence ($\beta = .205$ & P-value = .000), and emotional balance ($\beta = .276$ & P-value

= .000), and thus hypothesis was accepted from results that provide further clues towards mediation procedure to examine the mediation outcomes.

Mediation First Step (a)

Model Summary

R	R Square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.4476	.2004	.3648	94.7884	1.0000	338.0000	.0000

Coefficients of Regression

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	2.1468	.1251	17.1616	.0000	1.9007	2.3928
Physical Education	.3841	.0394	9.7359	.0000	.3065	.4617

Predicting Variable: Physical Education

Criterion Variable: Emotional Intelligence

Mediation Second & Third Steps (b & c)

Model Summary

R	R Square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.6764	.4575	.2058	167.2426	2.0000	337.0000	.0000

Table 4.14 Coefficients of Regression (H3)

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.1941	.1229	9.7184	.0000	.9524	1.4358
Emotional Intelligence	.3060	.0450	6.8038	.0000	.2175	.3945
Physical Education	.3559	.0421	8.4503	.0000	.2730	.4387

Predicting Variable: Physical Education, Emotional Intelligence

Criterion Variable: Cognitive Performance

Mediation Fourth Step (c)

Model Summary

R	R Square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.6060	.3672	.2394	175.8445	1.0000	338.0000	.0000

Coefficients of Regression

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.8511	.1217	15.2119	.0000	1.6117	2.0904

Physical	.4734	.0357	13.2606	.0000	.4032	.5436
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Education						
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Predicting Variable: Physical Education

Criterion Variable: Cognitive Performance

The mediation procedure was used in current study to confirm the mediating role of emotional intelligence in linking physical education and cognitive performance through four different and leading paths of mediation while determining the direct and indirect relationships among these research variables. The mediation procedure to examine the mediation hypothesis that whether the mediator partially mediated the relationship between independent and dependent variable or fully mediated the relationship. The results of mediation all four paths revealed that mediator (emotional intelligence) partially mediated the relationship between the physical education and cognitive performance due to decrease in coefficient value from (.4734) in direct relationship to (.3559) in indirect relationship while all the other requirements remained significant which thus confirmed the partial mediation and hypothesis about the mediation from these results is hence accepted in current study.

DISCUSSION

The relationship between work out and academic achievement is issue which is researched by numerous researchers and many of them confirm that exercise enhances attention and focusing on activities [31]. The emotional intelligence is cognitive function with balance in emotional stability, emotional balance, physical education, interaction of emotions and physical exercise with the various cognitive results [32]. Thus, the emotional stability is another factor, which influences cognitive functioning and can influence people in terms of concentration, information processing and problem solving. Consequently, there are studies that indicate that the cognitive performance of students is positively influenced by exercise performed in physical education from different perspectives [33]. It is not merely the subject to be taken but the pillar of whole upbringing and contributes to the physical and emotional development of the brain of student in different circumstances.

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physical education, emotional stability, emotional intelligence, and emotional balance proves the existence of the comprehensive system of comprehending the role of physical activity and emotional control in the processes of the mind [35]. Emotions are stable to keep a good degree of arousal required in cognition towards desired determinations [36]. According to system, it is necessary to consider the significance of the comprehensive educational programs that not only cover the mental and physical context but also the emotional and mental health to enable students to attain improved mental results in learning.

This model reveals that education systems must not only scale beyond the mere inclusion of cognitive skills, but also to include physical and emotional skills as well so to end up with fully developed students. Due to this, the physical education curriculum must address emotional self-control and emotional regulation development to enable development of higher order thinking in children and to enable children learn better [37]. The physical education has been indicated to be useful in emotional self-control positively influences academic [38]. Developing emotional self-control and emotional regulation and realization of what affects them will enable academic and policy planners to better develop physical education curriculum will emotionally stabilize and enable them to think more constructively and learn in a superior way [39]. Such statistics help understand that it is necessary to take into account emotional and physical condition of the student to create curriculum.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Through the application of emotional intelligence theories, the universities can persuade students to acquire skills to detect, interpret, and control emotions through integrating the efficient use of the self-reflection, feedback, and collaborations and in the co-curricular activities for the developments.
2. The institutions have to incorporate academic curriculum with the Unstructured Physical Education programs that are periodically planned and sequenced of these elements should be included as they form the basis of emotional stability that in turn improves cognitive performance towards success.
3. The policymakers are bound to accept physical education as possible inter-disciplinary tactic of cognitive growth in higher learning institution and offer the kind of leadership and thinking diverse abilities.

4. The academic counsellors and the teachers of physical education, in their endeavours to encourage emotional balance, especially in high stress academics, should be accorded the support and training in order to achieve better learning environments, mental stamina and constancy in a cognitive task.

DIRECTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

1. Some other psychological variables like mediators and moderators like academic pressure, motivation, mindfulness, social learning, and learning climate also need to be examined to see the effects of physical in terms of mental influences and enhancing the overall psycho-emotional growth of students.
2. To answer the complex research questions that are geared towards the understanding of the emotional/longevity of positive emotional period and negative emotional period inter-cognition, emotional stability, theories, sustained cognitive performance, developmental continuum in context of education.
3. It is expected that future studies in field of physical education will employ mixed research designs as quantitative and qualitative research designs will be used on both student and teacher populations as cognitive engagement through physical activity, exercise and sports in higher education institutions.
4. In higher education, the emotional stability, emotional intelligence, emotional balance, and cognitive performance also overlap and undercut across many educational systems, across, and within, in many disparate cultural contexts, academic disciplines, and gender towards attainment of desired outcomes.

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